

BigStuff: Care of Large Technology Objects

These are the proceedings of the BigStuff large technology workshop held at the Australian War Memorial in Canberra, Australia on the 29-30th September and 1st October 2004.

The proceedings include:

- written versions of 20 presentations;
- transcriptions of the question and answer sessions which followed most of the presentations;
- written versions of material presented at the poster session on Day 2 of the workshop;
- a transcription of the open discussion session held on Day 3 of the workshop: Future directions in the care of large technology;
- a group photo of the delegates;
- a list of the delegates.

Bibliographic information for the proceedings is as follows:

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